

SPOON EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

D5.1

WP 5, T5,1

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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- *PU = Public
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D5.1 SPOON EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

CHANGE HISTORY / REVIEW TABLE

v	Date	Beneficiary and description	Author
D1	04/04/2025	AIT shared the first outline for the framework for partner feedback.	Vitaliy Soloviy, Surya Knöbel, Gudrun Haindlmaier
D1	14/04/2025	CSCP provided feedback on the outline	Ahmad ur Rehman Hafiz
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D2	17/07/2025	SPOON partners provided feedback to the framework during a validation workshop	All partners
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D4	18/08/2025	HoC completed the technical review and provided feedback	Alessandro Galli
D5	21/08/2025	AIT revised the full draft and integrated feedback from CSCP and HoC	Vitaliy Soloviy, Surya Knöbel, Gudrun Haindlmaier, Beatrix Wepner, Sabine Neuberger
D5	22/08/2025	CSCP provided feedback and suggestions for changes	Arlind Xhelili, Francesca Grossi
D6	29/08/2025	AIT revised feedback and comments from CSCP and delivered the final version of D5.1	Vitaliy Soloviy, Surya Knöbel, Gudrun Haindlmaier, Beatrix Wepner, Sabine Neuberger
V1	31/08/2025	CSCP submitted the first version of the deliverable to the granting authority.	Arlind Xhelili

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
BCI	Behaviour Change Intervention
CS	Citizen Science
CSL	Citizen Science Lab
DMP	Data Management Plan
ESM	Experience Sampling Method
EU	European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IT	Information Technology
KIP	Key Impact Pathway
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PO	Project Objective
PR	Project Result
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SEF	SPOON Evaluation Framework
WP	Work Package

KEY TERMS

The presented terms are plain language definitions that will help to navigate the document. The interpretation has been tailored and adapted to the SPOON project needs and activities and is aimed primarily as a common reference, without exhaustively capturing the meaning behind the terms. More expansive definitions and descriptions are provided further as necessary.

Term	Basic definition
Sustainable Food System Transformation	A systemic shift toward sustainable, inclusive, and resilient food systems that support healthy diets, reduce environmental harm, and empower communities.
SPOON Evaluation	A collaborative process of evaluating SPOON activities, results, and outcomes that helps to learn along the way, enhance impact potential, and comprehensively evaluate project achievements.
Theory of Change	A conceptual model used in SPOON to articulate how and why change is expected to occur along the impact pathways.
Impact Pathway	A causal set of events describing how activities and outputs lead to outcomes and impacts, in line with project objectives.
Citizen Science Lab (CSL)	A core participatory mechanism of SPOON, which blends citizens science and living lab methods, where citizens act as both researchers and food system change agents.
Behaviour Change Intervention (BCI)	Co-designed and context-specific set of actions in the CSLs regions that aim to experiment, learn, and shift individual or collective food consumption behaviours.
SPOON Digital Toolset	A GDPR-compliant suite of tools, including a multi-media questionnaire, personal data wallet, data-sharing platform, and APIs, that enables people to collect, manage, and share their food-related data securely and transparently.
Food environment framework	A model used in SPOON to analyse the contexts in which people interact with food that helps with the identification of intervention points across the food system.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SPOON Evaluation Framework (SEF) sets the foundation for the monitoring and evaluation of the project's impact. This document presents the main building blocks of this process, including information on what SPOON has set out to achieve, how the monitoring and evaluation process has been designed, and an indication of how this process will be rolled out in practice, including the roles and responsibilities of project partners.

Theory of Change will be the backbone of the monitoring and evaluation process to help outline the cause-and-effect relationship between project activities, results, outcomes, as well as long-term impacts. These top-down conceptualisations are complemented with a recognition that change is a locally driven and open-ended process.

This dual perspective is reflected to different degrees across the four SPOON impact pathways, which are: (1) **Understand food system transformations**, collecting local insights to enhance healthy and sustainable food consumption, improve food security, and enable better choices; 2) **Shape food behaviours** by designing practical, sustainable and healthier solutions 3) **Promote digital innovation and data sharing** with the help of digital tools to analyse how people buy and consume food and by building trust in data sharing; 4) **Empower citizens and decisions-makers**, as well as other actors to participate in food system transformation by providing evidence and community perspectives to support smarter, more inclusive solutions.

These pathways capture the main areas of the expected project outcomes, while linking to the broad SPOON connects citizens, researchers, industries, civil society organisations, and policymakers to co-create a fairer, healthier, and more sustainable food future. A common understanding within the project is that a successful and long-lasting transformation requires systemic, participatory, and locally adapted approaches, reflected in specific project activities, such as the SPOON Citizen Science Labs (CSLs), Behaviour Change Interventions (BCIs), and the SPOON GDPR-compliant Digital Toolset. These activities will be deployed in the project's pilot regions, namely, Germany, Greece, Belgium, Slovenia, Italy, and Spain.

Building on these, SPOON will deploy more supra-level and outward-facing activities such as the SPOON Academy, a capacity-building programme to support the cascade of behavioural science and insights into various organisations' operations, and the recommendations package targeting various decision-makers on utilising the project learnings to advance solutions for healthier, more sustainable, and equitable food systems. These activities will be at the core of the SPOON's monitoring and evaluation, presented further in this report. To evaluate these activities in a structured way, SEF applies three components, see Table 1 SPOON evaluation components overview Table 1.

Table 1 SPOON evaluation components overview

Top- ↓ down	↑ Bottom-up	🌀 Exploratory
<i>How does SPOON deliver on its outputs, outcomes, and potential long-term impacts in line with the SPOON Pathways?</i>	<i>How do SPOON activities resonate with local needs? Which evaluation questions and indicators capture the activities in pilot regions?</i>	<i>What do SPOON partners and stakeholders learn along the way? Which interim outcomes and potential impacts have not been anticipated?</i>

This structure ensures that evaluation covers both planned intervention logic and the more dynamic processes of change. The evaluation is also informed by a set of guiding principles aiming to enable the transformation potential of citizen science. The evaluation process includes five main groups of activities that are summarised through short guiding questions that help project partners navigate the evaluation process.

Table 2 Step-by-step guide: how to use SEF in your work

Note: SPOON Partners:

Activity	Guiding Questions	Relevance
Conceptualisation Set the scene and understand your context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which SPOON pathways are most relevant to your work? Who needs to be involved to achieve the desired impacts? What are your community's food challenges? What's already happening in your local food system? 	
Capacity building Learn methods and focus on what matters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are your unique evaluation questions and indicators? What capacities do you need for evaluation? How do you make use of the evaluation insights? 	
Monitoring and data collection Use the monitoring toolkit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When and what kind of data should you collect? How will you collect inputs from local participants? What adjustments are needed to the monitoring methods? 	
Formative Evaluation Learn as you go	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is working well, and what needs to change? How can you enhance the impact potential? What enabling or limiting conditions are shaping results? What can we learn from each other and across the labs? 	
Final Evaluation Capture the big Picture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What data did you collect or might be missing? Which results and interim outcomes have you achieved? What signals of longer-term impact can be identified? What worked and what didn't? What can others learn to advance food system change? 	

1 INTRODUCTION

According to recent research, food systems are responsible for up to 37% of the global greenhouse gas emissions (Crippa et al., 2021) and if the trend is to continue, their climate impact can surge to 50–90% (Oakden et al., 2021). Conflicts, climate shocks, and widening inequalities have weakened global food supply chains. Despite abundant food in affluent nations, income inequality results in significant food insecurity. In Europe alone, about 38 million people lack access to sufficient, healthy food (IFOAM, n.d.). Addressing these interconnected issues requires multi-level knowledge, innovative technologies, behavioural shifts, and transformative policies that consider cultural practices influencing dietary habits.

Traditional top-down approaches to food system challenges are insufficient in today's rapidly changing landscape. The SPOON project proposes a paradigm shift by placing citizens' local realities and operational settings at the forefront of transformation through citizen science. The latter can be placed as a powerful tool in empowering communities to contribute to knowledge generation and fostering collaboration for a more inclusive and sustainable food system.

SPOON has selected six European locations as its project target regions: Braunschweig, Germany; Thessaloniki, Greece; Turin, Italy; Bruges, Belgium; Valencia, Spain; and Pomurje Region, Slovenia. They reflect diverse local contexts, geographical representation, varying climate conditions, and sustainability challenges. The selection also considered differences in local food production systems and accessibility to healthy and sustainable food, alongside the presence of food deserts or food swamps, where access to nutritious food is limited or unbalanced. Additionally, levels of food insecurity and the variety of thematic challenges faced by each location were key factors in the decision-making process.

By understanding the interplay between citizen science, consumer behaviours, and data sharing, SPOON aims to enhance context-specific, cross-sector, and data-driven decision-making for healthier, more sustainable diets and improved food security. In SPOON, citizens will actively participate in the research process and use innovative digital tools to collect, analyse, and interpret food data. The project will seek to:

- **Develop an analytical framework and increase understanding of factors** influencing healthy and sustainable food consumption
- **Implement Citizen Science Labs (CSLs) and Behaviour Change Interventions (BCI)** with citizens and food stakeholders to collect, visualise, and interpret data on consumers' consumption behaviours and their local food purchasing and consumption environments
- **Create and deploy the SPOON Digital Toolset** that includes a multimedia questionnaire generator and a personal data wallet to enable data collection and analysis (citizen science)
- **Establish a GDPR-compliant data governance framework** focusing on privacy, data sharing, and interoperability
- **Produce guidelines and a capacity-building programme** for citizen science and consumer behaviour change projects aiming to exploit, replicate, and accelerate project learnings, insights, and results
- **Draft policy recommendations** to enhance data-driven policies through better use of citizen data, digital tools, and cross-sector collaboration.

Through its initiatives, especially the CSLs, BCI, and the citizen science Digital Toolset, the project will address several critical topics. It will investigate food waste by identifying the types of food most frequently discarded and why, and strategies to reduce waste. Another focus will be the food environments and their influence on consumer behaviour and food choices, as well as transparency and accountability across the food supply chain, and their impact on purchasing and eating behaviours. By empowering citizens and engaging food stakeholders across the supply chain, SPOON aims to spark a collective journey towards a more just, sustainable, and resilient food future for all. The project will also explore food insecurity, examining factors that affect access to sustainable, healthy food for vulnerable communities and the mechanisms driving these disparities. Finally, SPOON will analyse how demographic factors shape sustainable food consumption patterns and behaviours.

The SPOON SEF lays the foundation for monitoring and evaluating the project's impact. It outlines what SPOON aims to achieve, how the evaluation process has been designed, and how it will be implemented in practice. The framework also defines the roles and responsibilities of project partners to ensure coordinated execution.

To ensure the framework reflects the needs of all involved, it was developed collaboratively based on a series of workshops with project partners, covering:

- *Sense-making*: Building a shared understanding of the intended impact and the expectations surrounding the framework.
- *Co-creation*: Jointly designing and refining the evaluation criteria, key questions, and approach to establishing baselines.
- *Validation*: Ensuring the framework is coherent, comprehensive, and attentive to diverse perspectives and partner needs.

The framework is further presented in three chapters. The first one describes how SPOON approaches impact building on the project's theory of change. The second chapter details evaluation design and its main building blocks. The third chapter presents key implementation activities and responsibilities, setting the stage for monitoring and formative evaluation, which further deepen and operationalise specific framework components in separate deliverables.

2 APPROACH TO IMPACT

To monitor and evaluate SPOON's impact, one first needs to understand what kind of impact that is being created are trying to create and *how* this is pursued. This chapter, therefore, presents an overview of SPOON's understanding of impact. SPOON objectives, activities, results, outcomes, and impacts are grouped around four different, but complementary, SPOON pathways that present coherent storylines about how SPOON will approach impact creation. **Error! Reference source not found.** demonstrates a simplified schematic representation of the assumption about causality between activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts, as well as how they link to project objectives. Further sections highlight some critical elements of SPOON impact creation, with particular focus on activities, SPOON pathways, and impact.

Figure 1 SPOON Pathways (schematic representation)

2.1 SPOON ACTIVITIES

Several activities will be undertaken within the SPOON project to support its objectives, expected impact, and overall ambition. Most of the project activities will be implemented strictly within the pilot regions. These activities include the CSLs, BCIs, and the SPOON Digital Toolset. Once fully co-created and tested in the pilot regions, the SPOON Digital Toolset will ideally be rolled out in other European countries, allowing people from diverse local contexts to contribute their data and shape food systems across Europe.

To support implementation in pilot regions, SPOON partners do background research, design the CSL methodology, project communications, and data management. SPOON will also have SPOON Academy and the multi-stakeholder recommendations, building upon the insights and findings collected from the regional pilot activities.

CSLs, a combination of citizen science and living labs, will engage individuals and local communities in the co-creation of knowledge and solutions to promote healthier and more sustainable food behaviours. These labs will allow citizens to actively participate in the scientific process by collecting and analysing data, shaping the solutions, and contributing to research findings. In addition to lay people, the CSLs will bring together food stakeholders, such as local farmers, retailers, and policymakers, to ensure that solutions are practical and tailored to the needs of each community. By empowering people to become active contributors, the CSLs foster ownership and commitment to the success of sustainable food initiatives.

BCIs will be implemented to test different strategies for influencing food behaviours in real-life settings. These interventions will be co-designed by local citizens and food stakeholders to ensure that they are contextually relevant and culturally sensitive. The BCIs will be conducted across multiple localities to capture a diverse range of consumer behaviours and the challenges they face in adopting healthier and more sustainable food practices. By applying a localized approach, the BCIs aim to identify barriers, assess the effectiveness of different solutions, and create behaviour change models that can be scaled or replicated in other regions.

The **SPOON Digital Toolset** will enable secure data collection, analysis, and interpretation while ensuring full control for citizens over their personal data. This toolset includes a customizable multimedia questionnaire tool that is customizable for interactive and engaging data collection, enabling participants to share detailed insights into their food consumption habits. Additionally, the personal data wallet will allow citizens to manage and store their own data securely. The toolset will also feature the DATAU platform, which ensures transparent data sharing where participants can explicitly consent and track past permissions. Through APIs, the toolset will integrate with other tools like DATALAKE to enable seamless data flow and interoperability. It will be governed by a GDPR-compliant data governance framework, prioritizing privacy, consent management, and data interoperability, ensuring citizens' data is securely handled and shared in a responsible, transparent manner.

A comprehensive capacity-building program, **the SPOON Academy**, will be developed to support citizen science and consumer behaviour change initiatives. This program will provide guidelines and tools for organizations and individuals interested in replicating and scaling the project's findings and methodologies. The capacity-building effort will focus on training local stakeholders, including researchers, businesses, CSOs, and policymakers, in best practices for conducting citizen science projects, designing behaviour change interventions, and utilizing insights to develop effective solutions. By strengthening the capacity of local actors, it will ensure that the project's insights are effectively disseminated, replicated, and adopted across Europe, accelerating the transition to healthier and more sustainable food systems.

SPOON will draft **multi-stakeholder recommendations**, with a focus on policy, that aim to strengthen the role of data-driven approaches in promoting healthier, more sustainable, and equitable food consumption. These recommendations will focus on ensuring that citizen-

generated data, alongside insights from CSLs and BCIs, is effectively integrated into policy-making. By incorporating local, context-specific data, these policies will be better aligned with the diverse needs and challenges of different communities, enabling tailored interventions that support sustainable food choices. The recommendations will also emphasize the importance of transparent data governance frameworks to protect privacy while fostering trust in the process. Ultimately, the goal is to guide policies that not only encourage healthier eating habits and reduce environmental impacts but also ensure that food systems are accessible, fair, and inclusive for all, contributing to a more equitable transition toward sustainable food futures.

Enhancing the transformative potential of the project achievements may be achieved through **communication, dissemination, and exploitation**, as well as **synergetic activities** with other projects and initiatives, transformative learning and reflexivity, enhancing inclusivity and justice of outcomes, as well as exploration of novel uses of results and potential for triggering deep leverage points (Davelaar, 2021). Identification of options on impact enhancement will be subject to formative evaluation activities.

2.2 SPOON PATHWAYS

SPOON delivers its expected impacts through four pathways (see Figure 1 presented earlier in this chapter). SPOON pathways present storylines around expected outcomes that integrate sets of project objectives, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts. The pathways integrate the theory of change approach with insights from food system transformation and citizen science literature, and results of co-creation with project partners.

SPOON pathways are distinct but also interlinked, while some activities contribute to more than one pathway. The SPOON pathways do not mirror the Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) of Horizon Europe, but integrate them into the project logic, with applicable indicators distributed across the different SPOON pathways (to be presented in the D5.2 SPOON Monitoring Toolkit). Each pathway serves as a reference point for monitoring and evaluation. For every pathway, specific elements are included: its objectives, the key results and expected outcomes, and the relevant Horizon Europe KIPs. The following subsections outline each impact pathway in greater detail.

2.2.1 UNDERSTANDING FOOD SYSTEM TRANSFORMATIONS

SPOON recognises within the current food system trajectories there's still a great opportunity and space to deliver on human wellbeing and environmental sustainability (Edwards et al., 2024a; Janin et al., 2023). Transforming these systems requires approaches that are locally relevant and address broader sustainability goals (Carriedo et al., 2022; Slater et al., 2022). The SPOON pathway, therefore, aims at deepening understanding of food system transformation with a focus on local food environments, how they enable or constrain access to healthy and sustainable food, as well as shape food behaviours and citizen engagement in data sharing.

Food system innovation has often advanced through technological solutions such as precision agriculture, gene-edited crops, and dietary supplements. SPOON broadens this view by integrating social, behavioural, cultural, and economic dimensions, emphasising participation and everyday practices like buying, storing, and consuming food, as well as managing food waste, to create more inclusive and systemic change.

Better understanding food system transformation also requires considering how various governance scales and actors interact, shaping food system priorities (Dorninger et al., 2020; Lajoie-O'Malley et al., 2020; Moallemi et al., 2024), as well as connections to issues such as the climate crisis, water, biodiversity, social equality, and power (Dorninger et al., 2020; Federica Grant et al., 2023; Sonnino et al., 2019).

Table 3 SPOON Pathway 1: Understand food system transformations

Component	Description
Objectives	PO1: Develop accurate and context-specific knowledge of local food environments and translate this into actionable insights for policy and practice
Key activities	Co-creation of knowledge with citizens and communities in CSLs Background research on food system dynamics, barriers to citizen data collection, and behavioural barriers and drivers for S&H food consumption Collecting food consumption data using the SPOON Digital Toolset
Key Results	PR1: Co-developed innovative CS projects. PR9: Open access anonymized datasets PR7: Database of best CS practices in food system transformation
Expected Outcome	EO1: Citizens, researchers, and decision-makers gain a deeper, actionable understanding of food consumption behaviour and influencing factors, supporting evidence-based interventions
KIP Contributions	KIP1: Creating high-quality new knowledge KIP3: Fostering diffusion of knowledge & Open Science

2.2.2 SHAPING FOOD BEHAVIORS

SPOON recognises the importance of contexts in which people interact with food, including how they access food, the availability of various options, and the norms and conditions under which choices are made, considering how different elements of the food environment shape people's choices (Downs et al., 2020; Marshall et al., 2021; Turner et al., 2018).

This pathway underpins project activities on the establishment and implementation of CSLs, the co-design and implementation of BCIs, the creation of GDPR-compliant digital tools (e.g., personal data wallet, DataU platform, multimedia questionnaire generator), and the delivery of the decision makers' capacity-building programme-SPOON Academy. They are complemented by strategic capacity-building for local project partners to connect CSLs and BCIs with local priorities; formative evaluation feedback loops and peer learning to refine actions; and purposeful impact-enhancement measures such as synergies with other initiatives, advancing political advocacy, and integrating intervention insights into policy and

governance frameworks that influence contexts in which food behaviours unfold. Together, these activities address not only changes in food environments but also people's capabilities, motivation, and access to solutions, creating a socio-political context for sustained, scalable impacts.

SPOON draws on the food consumption journey and food environments framework (Turner et al., 2018) to inform its understanding of the contexts in which people acquire and consume food. They help to interpret how personal consumption choices and local conditions, such as affordability, convenience, desirability, and accessibility, shape behaviours and intersect with issues like food insecurity. These insights guide the design and evaluation of activities within the CSLs and BCIs, ensuring that interventions are rooted in lived realities and responsive to the specific challenges and opportunities of each location.

Table 4 SPOON Pathway 2: Shaping food behaviours

Component	Description
Objectives	PO4: Increased agency of citizens and communities to adopt and sustain healthier and more sustainable food choices and practices
Key activities	<p>Implementing BCIs co-designed with citizens.</p> <p>Promote healthier and more sustainable food behaviours via CLSs engagement</p> <p>Citizen participation in scientific processes via SPOON digital tools set in CSLs</p> <p>Deployment of the SPOON Academy to build local actors' capacity to support CS and consumer behaviour change initiatives</p> <p>Facilitating peer learning and iterative feedback processes to enhance impact (formative evaluation)</p>
Key Results	PR2: Co-designed BCIs PR3: SPOON Academy capacity-building programme; PR4: Digital tools supporting behaviour change; PR6: Policy recommendations informed by generated knowledge
Expected Outcome	EO2: Demonstrated positive changes in individual behaviour towards healthy & sustainable food consumption
KIP Contributions	<p>KIP4: Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges</p> <p>KIP6: Strengthening uptake of R&I in society</p>

2.2.3 PROMOTING DIGITAL INNOVATION AND DATA SHARING

A critical challenge for food system transformation is ensuring that the data driving change is governed in a responsible, transparent, fair, and viable manner. Without this, there is a risk that data use reinforces inequalities or locks food systems into unsustainable trajectories, leading to less trust and engagement from consumers and citizens.

Digitalization of the food system has accelerated in recent years, driven by data collection on consumption preferences, choices, and patterns through nutrition apps, digital marketing, and microtargeting (Granheim et al., 2022). While much of this data is currently collected to meet commercial needs, often with limited transparency, digitalization also offers opportunities for anticipatory policies, democratizing food systems, enhancing accountability, and enabling broader participation. Harnessed responsibly, it could help identify systemic and structural issues such as food deserts, inequalities, and vulnerabilities while supporting more resilient supply chains and inclusive food systems. (Greenthal et al., 2024; OECD, 2021).

Given the broader corporate interests and regimes around food, the data can be used for targeting and shaping consumer preferences (Fuentes et al., 2021; Granheim et al., 2022). Growing public awareness, combined with varying levels of trust in digital technologies, uneven data literacy, and digital divides, has contributed to a degree of caution among citizens when it comes to intentionally sharing food-related data. (Fuentes et al., 2021; Tsolakidis et al., 2024). This highlights the importance of building collective and individual agency of citizens and trustful interactions among food actors for impact creation in SPOON.

SPOON addressed this challenge by developing a Digital Toolset (e.g., a GDPR-compliant personal data wallet, data hub, and data sharing platforms) and embedding its use in CSLs. Together with value chain actors (e.g., retailers, HoReCa¹, food suppliers), this toolset enables citizens to generate, control, and share their food data in transparent and empowering ways. SPOON connects top-down policy priorities with bottom-up citizen science approaches, strengthening both public participation and scientific inquiry in food system transformation.

Table 5 SPOON Pathway 3: Promoting digital innovation and data sharing

Component	Description
Objectives	PO5: Strengthen citizens' confidence, skills, and agency to control, share, and use their food data for healthier and more sustainable food system choices.
Key activities	<p>Developing and deploying the SPOON Digital Toolset, including the multimedia questionnaire generator, personal data wallet, the DATAU platform, and DATALAKE to ensure data interoperability via APIs</p> <p>Establishing a GDPR-compliant data governance framework,</p> <p>Embedding digital tools within CSL activities</p>

¹ Hotels, Restaurants and Catering

Key Results	PR4: SPOON Digital Toolset PR5: Data governance framework PR8: SWOT analysis of digital tools; PR9 Open access & anonymised datasets of personal food data
Expected Outcome	EO3: Increased trust and participation of citizens in data sharing, demonstrated by uptake of SPOON Digital Toolsets and integration of citizen-generated data into decision-making processes.
KIP Contributions	KIP3: Fostering open source & data diffusion KIP6: Strengthening uptake of R&I in society KIP7: Generating innovation-based growth

2.2.4 EMPOWERING CITIZENS AND DECISION MAKERS

Even ambitious, technically sound solutions frequently fail due to low social acceptability, lack of political will, or institutional fragmentation. SPOON addresses this by embedding co-created experimentation and capacity-building into real-life local food environments, ensuring solutions are not only co-designed but also context-appropriate and adaptable.

SPOON's approach to impact is informed by recognizing that changing food systems requires not just the adoption of new solutions and practices, but also addressing underlying norms, governance, and local contexts, “activating the agency and capacities of individuals and collectives to transform systems and cultures at scale.” (O’Brien et al., 2023). Building on the SPOON scope of activities and expected results, it is also important to consider the broader contexts that influence impact creation. These include responsiveness to local needs, shifts in food system conditions, emerging enablers and barriers, and wider societal reconfigurations (Edwards et al., 2024; Moallemi et al., 2024; von Gönner et al., 2023).

SPOON adopts an understanding of citizen science outlined in SPOON’s CSLs framework (to yet be finalised, and taking precedence in all CS concepts to be utilised in the project), which positions citizens as co-researchers actively involved in designing, collecting, analysing, and sharing knowledge, in line with the principles of the European Citizen Science Association² (Schade et al., 2024; Southern Denmark University, Kolding, Denmark & Wilde, 2021; von Gönner et al., 2023), while also extending the focus on the potential of citizen science to enable transformative change in targeted domains (Schade et al., 2024; Southern Denmark University, Kolding, Denmark & Wilde, 2021; von Gönner et al., 2023).

The project sees CS as an approach that holds transformative potential for inclusive and participatory knowledge creation and food system transformations, building on tacit and local knowledge in a way that traditional scientific research cannot. This means producing knowledge in close connection with real-world contexts and in dialogue with the people affected, rather than following a one-way, expert-driven process where research stays within disciplinary boundaries and is mainly expected to lead to change (Gibbons et al., 1994; Horcea-Milcu et al., 2024).

² European Citizen Science Association: [About ECSA – European Citizen Science Association \(ECSA\)](#)

CSLs in SPOON combine citizen science and living lab approaches (Brons et al., 2022; Schade et al., 2024; von Gönner et al., 2023) to create locally embedded spaces where citizen participation, food system challenges, and co-created research agendas intersect. By bridging scientific inquiry with civic engagement (Rambonnet et al., 2019), they enhance the relevance, legitimacy, and societal value of citizen-generated knowledge while fostering capacity building, social learning (van Noordwijk et al., 2021), and cross-actor collaboration.

The pathway focuses on how CSL activities enable cross-actor collaboration for data-driven decision-making, strengthen and sustain citizen influence in food system governance, and ensure the uptake of project outputs in policy and practice. It will examine citizen empowerment and changes in citizens' confidence, skills, and willingness to participate in decision-making processes, as well as their sustained engagement beyond the project, along with continuity and replication of CSL impacts and broader societal impact. It will also assess the translation into policy, and other solutions, and how insights from CSL research are synthesised into actionable multi-stakeholder and policy recommendations and best practices, the extent to which these are taken up by decision-makers at local, regional, and EU levels, and how effectively CSLs foster two-way communication and collaboration among stakeholders and across sectors.

These aspects will be assessed through evidence tracking of policy uptake, replication cases of BCIs and SPOON Academy, and new collaborations; surveys and interviews capturing citizen perceptions of empowerment, capacity building, and influence using the SPOON digital toolkit and monitoring toolkit; observation and documentation of CSL workshops, co-creation processes, and output analysis of policy briefs, recommendations, and best practice documentation.

Table 6 SPOON Pathway 4: Empowering citizens and decision makers

Component	Detail
Objectives	PO2: Increased capacity for data-driven decisions PO3: Pathways for cross-sector collaboration
Key Activities	Engaging citizens and food system actors in CSLs to co-create knowledge and collaboratively address food system challenges in local contexts Building capacity through the SPOON Academy Producing and disseminating policy recommendations and best practices derived from CSL and BCI findings Supporting data collection and participation in CSLs through the deployment of SPOON digital tools
Key Results	PR6: Policy recommendations package PR7: Best practice database
Expected Outcome	EO4: Increased empowerment of citizens to engage in decision-making for food system transformation

KIP
Contributions

KIP4: Addressing EU policy priorities
KIP6: Strengthening societal uptake of R&I

2.3 SPOON LONG-TERM IMPACT

SPOON creates long-term impact primarily across the Horizon Europe scientific, social and economic, and technological impact pathways. Specifically, SPOON contributes to five impact pathways of Horizon Europe as specified further.

SPOON enables long-term scientific impacts through generating new knowledge on how people consume food, what influences their choices, and what motivates or prevents them from sharing personal food data through scientific publications (KIP 1 – Creating high quality new knowledge) through literature reviews on topics such as systemic interventions and barriers and enablers to sustainable food consumption, as well as making openly accessible its GDPR compliant datasets and the database of best practices, recommendations on multi-sectoral collaborations and trainings through the SPOON Academy (KIP 3 – Fostering diffusion of new knowledge and data science).

SPOON enables long-term social impact by addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges (KIP 4), such as the Sustainable Development Goals, EU Climate targets, Farm to Fork Strategy, Food 2030 R&I pathways, and the New European Bauhaus through R&I, with particular focus on issues of priorities that address matters of food security, availability, accessibility, inclusivity, as well as healthy and sustainable food behaviours and food waste reduction. Through adopting the citizen science labs approach, people are actively involved in co-designing solutions while diverse food system actors are enabled through and multi-stakeholder recommendations (KIP 5 – Strengthening the uptake).

SPOON enables its long-term technological and economic impacts by driving innovation-led growth by helping food system actors better understand consumer needs – supporting the transition to more sustainable and healthier food systems (KIP 7 – Generating innovation-based growth), particularly harnessing the power of digitalisation and data sharing. SPOON puts particular focus on gaining insights from consumer realities and enabling better decision-making by various food system actors, such as retailers, farmers, food distributors, HoReCa, and business-support organisations.

3 EVALUATION DESIGN

3.1 BACKGROUND

SPOON evaluation builds on several complementary aspects, as outlined below, which guide the design of evaluation activities.

Table 7 Key aspects of evaluation

Aspect	Overview
SPOON Pathways	SPOON evaluation is conducted along the SPOON Pathways presented in the previous chapter.
Evaluation Components	Evaluation includes three complementary components that do not overlap and are represented in each of the SPOON pathways: top-down, bottom-up, and exploratory. In some instances, bottom-up and exploratory components may reflect aspects not initially considered within the pathways.
Evaluation Questions	Evaluation questions are structured along the SPOON pathways and cover different components and types of evaluation. These questions are translated into plain language and detailed within the various evaluation activities. The evaluation questions will be provided in the monitoring toolkit and linked to activities by partners in different work packages and pilot regions.
Indicators	The indicators operationalise evaluation questions to collect evidence of implementation and change. They may be qualitative or quantitative.

SPOON's impact evaluation approach is anchored in Kieslinger et al. (2018) typology of citizen science impacts, with insights from other citizen science evaluation approaches (van Noordwijk et al., 2021; von Gönner et al., 2023; Wehn et al., 2021). Kieslinger distinguishes three evaluation dimensions (scientific, participant, and broader) and two evaluation types (process-based and outcomes-based). As part of the framework design, AIT conducted a workshop where project partners prioritised relevant evaluation questions that have been part of the original framework (Kieslinger et al., 2018). The results of this activity have informed the integration of evaluation questions into SPOON pathways. These questions will be further mapped against different project activities and operationalised into indicators within the monitoring toolkit. The original evaluation dimensions and types thus serve as background for the conceptualisation of evaluation questions and indicators, but they are not central to the evaluation activities as such. It is still, however, useful to consider what is covered by different

dimensions and types of evaluation as background. The approach allows tracking not only what is achieved but also how it is achieved, and who benefits along the way.

Table 8 The interface between evaluation dimensions and types

Note: based on citizen science evaluation frameworks (Kieslinger et al., 2018, 2022; ZSI - Centre for Social Innovation et al., 2022) and the workshops with project partners.

Dimension	Process and Feasibility <i>How activities are designed, implemented, and experienced by partners, citizens, and stakeholders</i>	Outcome and Impact <i>Project results, their outcomes, and impact potential</i>
Scientific	Knowledge-co production Data quality and standards Ethics, data protection, and IPR Openness and interfaces	Scientific knowledge and publications New fields of research and research structures New knowledge resources
Participant	Target group alignment Participation intensity and quality Participant diversity Facilitation, communication Feedback mechanisms	Knowledge, skills, competencies Scientific literacy Behavioural change and ownership Motivation and engagement
Socio-ecological, Technological, and Economic	Target group alignment Active involvement Two-way communication Collaboration and synergies	Citizen empowerment Uptake of tools by stakeholders Governance and political advocacy

3.2 EVALUATION PRINCIPLES

SPOON's evaluation approach bridges principles of evaluation coming from citizen science and transformative evaluation. The broader emerging approach of transformative evaluation aligns with citizen science but also puts particular focus on “how project activities are contributing to transformation” and “how evaluation of project activities can most effectively assist transformation efforts”. The SPOON evaluation builds on twelve principles for transformation-focused evaluation to acknowledge complexity, address power dynamics, and ensure purpose. SPOON implemented eleven out of the twelve transformative evaluation principles (Buckton et al., 2025), omitting only the foresight principle as it is not directly reflected in project activities.

Table 9 Principles for transformation-focused evaluation

Note: adapted from (Buckton et al., 2025)

Principle	Evaluation principle and its application in SPOON
Acknowledging complexity	<p><i>Complex systems principle: Treat evaluands as nested systems with complex interactions.</i> SPOON operates amidst multiple transformations across different scales, from international to local, each represented by different actors and interests. For instance, national food strategies reflect broad needs but might not capture local realities within pilot regions.</p> <p><i>Context principle: Recognize that evaluands are unique and need context-adapted evaluation.</i> SPOON pilots have different baselines and priorities, requiring an approach that recognises this diversity.</p> <p><i>Detective principle: draw on multiple, mixed methods to improve understanding about transformations in an uncertain, multi-reality, and hard-to-control world.</i> SPOON evaluation draws on mixed methods and different actor insights.</p> <p><i>Developmental principle: Remain agile and developmental (continual reflection, feedback, learning, and adaptation).</i> SPOON adopts a formative evaluation approach that considers how the CSLs, BSI, and project activities are running and then responds and makes adjustments where necessary.</p>
Power-sensitiveness	<p><i>Justice principle: Promote justice in power relations, rights, and the use of knowledge.</i> SPOON has established evaluation criteria and questions that prioritize participation and inclusivity.</p> <p><i>Power Shift Principle: Shift power towards evaluation users and blur the evaluator-evaluated dichotomy.</i> SPOON will include citizens in co-evaluation activities in the formative and final evaluation.</p> <p><i>Autonomous evaluation principle: Support autonomous evaluation practice, including adopting clearer ethical and critical stances.</i> SPOON gives autonomy for tailoring some of the monitoring methods and indicators to the local aims and needs of the CSLs. It's a bottom-up and exploratory evaluation that complements the top-down approach.</p> <p><i>Partnership principle: Cultivate mutualistic partnerships of knowledge and action.</i> SPOON pilots feature co-creation knowledge with citizens, which is translated into action through various SPOON activities.</p>
Evaluation for a purpose	<p><i>Values principle: work with evaluands to surface and reflexively question various values in transformation processes, ensuring that transformational values are upheld.</i> SPOON addresses local values and norms around food, participation, and data sharing.</p>

Learning principle: Embrace an evaluation culture centred around ongoing learning. SPOON formative evaluation is centred around learning.

Transformation principle: Focus on evaluating and supporting systemic transformations towards regenerative futures. SPOON activities include multi-stakeholder recommendations and CSLs, while the broader project conceptualisation considers the need to create enabling conditions and remove barriers to food system transformation.

3.3 EVALUATION COMPONENTS

SPOON evaluation within each impact pathway integrates three core components.

- **Top-down alignment** – assessing activities and results along the SPOON Pathways with evaluation questions and indicators also informed by the relevant Key Impact Pathways – see SPOON long-term impact (to be detailed in the monitoring toolkit)
- **Bottom-up relevance** – capturing locally driven impacts and orientations from CSLs and pilots and connecting them to overall project goals (includes tailoring of evaluation questions to indicators to lab realities).
- **Exploratory learning** – identifying and analysing impacts that were not initially anticipated but emerge through implementation (enabled through tailored evaluation questions embedded in monitoring and formative evaluation activities)

The first two components aim to highlight the importance of the interface between top-down and bottom-up processes in food system transformation governance (Conti et al., 2025; Eicken et al., 2021), acknowledging the distinct potential of living labs and citizen science (Brons et al., 2022; Hölsgens et al., 2023; Schade et al., 2024). The third component is exploratory and aims to explore and work with impacts that are beyond what has been initially anticipated (Pel & Stirling, 2024), but what becomes apparent throughout the project, both at the level of work package activities and within the pilots.

The bottom-up evaluation component includes the definition of local baseline conditions, the formulation of CSL-specific priority intervention domains and priorities, adaptation of some evaluation questions and indicators, or the formulation of additional evaluation questions and indicators to reflect, as well as participation of pilot coordinators and potentially, other local actors in co-evaluation activities. It is particularly important to consider that CSLs do not start from scratch and are embedded in various local contexts that influence their activities (Janin et al., 2023; Mourre et al., 2024).

Through engaging with pilot coordinators, the evaluation aims to gain an understanding of the key peculiarities related to baseline conditions that will influence the potential to generate impact and the focus of CSL activities. These baselines help inform the assumptions and priorities that guide each CSL's activities.

Table 10 Key baseline conditions

Baselines	Description and examples
Food culture and norms	Locally, CSLs are shaped by existing food cultures and traditions, which define normative dietary patterns, food-related behaviours, and social perceptions about food. This influences how communities engage with the idea of healthy and sustainable food and shapes the relevance of intervention strategies. While some CSLs reflect gastronomic traditions and communal food practices (Thessaloniki, Turin), others face challenges of "food swamps" and limited access to healthy and sustainable options (Bruges).
National and regional food policies	National and regional policies may feature different priorities, such as reducing food waste, ensuring food security, promoting healthy diets, or supporting short supply chains and local production. Some CSLs are deeply embedded in municipal strategies and food councils (e.g., Valencia, Turin), while others connect more with grassroots and local civic initiatives (Braunschweig, Pomurje).
Participation cultures	Cultures and traditions of civic engagement may vary widely across CSL locations, e.g., countries with developed R&I systems are better positioned to engage relevant actors. This also depends on how SPOON is positioned and perceived locally. We have yet to gain initial knowledge about differences in participation cultures across contexts.
Focus areas	Each CSL engages with local food environments with a focus on specific topics and intervention domains (e.g., availability, convenience, affordability). Some CSLs focus on food security and access (Valencia, Turin), while others aim to reduce food waste (Braunschweig, Thessaloniki) or support supply chain innovation (Pomurje). This shapes CSL's priorities, ranging from behaviours linked to expiry and waste (Braunschweig), to barriers in H&S food access (Valencia, Turin), and circular economy (Thessaloniki, Pomurje).
Data sharing cultures and policies	Different degrees of openness and traditions in data sharing cultures and policies also shape CSL activities and expected impacts. Willingness to collect and share data varies among citizens and food actors, influenced by national frameworks, institutional trust, previous experiences, and social norms. These conditions are yet to be identified.
Cost and affordability of healthy food	The relative price of healthy and sustainable food compared to cheaper, less nutritious options influences access and dietary choices. In Bruges, fast food is often cheaper than fresh produce; in Valencia, local produce is abundant but is costly for vulnerable groups.
Socio-economic inequalities and vulnerabilities	Income levels, unemployment, and social safety nets affect households' ability to access H&S food and determine baseline levels of food insecurity. Turin and Valencia face food poverty challenges; in Pomurje, rural-urban divides affect accessibility.
Structural factors	For example, the dominance of supermarkets versus alternative outlets (farmers' markets, cooperatives) determines the food options available to communities. Braunschweig benefits from vending machines and local shops offering fresh produce, while Bruges is characterised by supermarket dominance and widespread unhealthy outlets.
Trust in institutions and governance	Levels of trust in public authorities, NGOs, and scientific institutions affect both participation in CSLs and willingness to share data. In Valencia and Turin, municipal food councils provide trusted entry points; in Pomurje, scepticism about sustainability claims requires stronger trust-building.

Recognising and analysing these baseline conditions is critical for evaluating the impact and outcomes of the CSLs' activities. They provide the lens through which process and outcome evaluations must be interpreted, ensuring that assessments of success or failure reflect not only project performance but also the specific enabling or constraining conditions of each location. Accordingly, considering the baseline conditions of each CSL will be embedded in SPOON's evaluation design, drawing on initial surveys, open data sources, and formative CSL evaluation, to ground findings in local realities.

Rather than focusing on a pre-defined scope like the two previous evaluation components, exploratory evaluation provides an open-ended and bottom-up perspective to evaluation. As part of initial lab activities, formative evaluation, and final evaluation, project stakeholders will be invited to map out actual and potential project outcomes and impacts not captured by previous questions, including positive and negative aspects, direct and indirect, as well as broader co-benefits and trade-offs perceived in their contexts and communities.

It has a distinct transformative aspect, requiring ongoing learning, critical reflexivity, and adaptation along the way, enabled by formative evaluation and informed by changing needs and the emergence of new factors that impact project potential for success (Carriedo et al., 2022; Dorninger et al., 2020; Edwards et al., 2024b; Kok et al., 2023; Otieno et al., 2023; Slater et al., 2022) drawing on concepts such as entry points for acceleration of transformations (Moallemi et al., 2024), deep leverage points (Davelaar, 2021) and transformative outcomes (Kanger et al., 2025) as guidance for reflection, to be further elaborated in coordination with WP 1 research on systemic interventions and serving to support identification and formulation of pilot activities.

Exploratory evaluation particularly highlights a more reflexive and critical standpoint on impact creation, aiming to foster new avenues for future action and more careful fine-tuning of evaluation trajectories. This lens particularly focuses on systemic, emergent, open-ended, and unintended impacts. It aims to broaden the understanding of project impact and deepen participatory, bottom-up, complexity-focused, and qualitative aspects. Exploratory evaluation enables appreciation of the diversity of local and actor-specific frames and assumptions about change, and the potential of art-based and other creative and transdisciplinary approaches that are not easy to capture with a standard list of questions. This component also enhances the sensemaking and interpretation of data, enabling project partners to track progress and better understand what is working and why. SPOON evaluation is implemented through five main types of activities detailed in the next section.

4 IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 EVALUATION ACTIVITIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

This section outlines how SEF is implemented through five main activities: conceptualisation, capacity building, monitoring and data collection, formative evaluation, and final evaluation.

These activities only partially follow a step-wise approach, as some activities are continuous (monitoring) or iterative (formative evaluation).

Table 11 Overview of evaluation activities

Activity	Description
<p>Conceptualisation</p>	<p>Builds a shared understanding of the project’s impact potential and how partners contribute to it, laying the foundation for monitoring, data collection, and evaluation. Partners co-design impact pathways, define evaluation questions and indicators, while pilot coordinators reflect on local baseline conditions and priorities. This stage concludes with finalising the SPOON Evaluation Framework and the first version of the Monitoring Toolkit. Some elements of conceptualisation may happen later in the project, i.e., in the evaluation questions and indicators need to be updated to reflect the focus on the BCIs.</p>
<p>Capacity Building</p>	<p>Includes training on the Monitoring Toolkit and formative evaluation for WP leads and the Impact Board, and tailored guidance on applying methods provided by AIT as necessary, responding to the needs of specific partners or CSLs. Capacity building is integrated into “Train the Trainers” and other project-level activities, with additional workshops organised by AIT if needed. The activity ensures all responsible partners (WP leads, Pilot coordinators) can implement monitoring and data collection, know what they have to submit and when, and can also interpret the results of the evaluation.</p>
<p>Monitoring & Data Collection</p>	<p>WP and Pilot coordinators use the SPOON Monitoring Toolkit to implement monitoring and data collection in line with WP and pilot timelines. As the project advances, the toolkit is updated with feedback to remain relevant to changing conditions and project needs. The activity results in timely and regular data being ready for submission to AIT directly by WP leads or through the Impact Board by the Pilot coordinators.</p>
<p>Formative Evaluation</p>	<p>Formative evaluation is conducted annually and complemented by mini-formative evaluations tailored to specific project stages or partners. In preparation, WP leads and Pilot coordinators submit interim data and complete short surveys distributed by AIT. During workshops, partners and stakeholders jointly reflect on achievements, challenges, and enabling or limiting factors. The activity results in a summary of insights developed by AIT covering both the project overall and specific WPs or CSLs as applicable.</p>

Final Evaluation	Final evaluation triangulates evidence across the project to assess implementation of activities, achievement of results, interim outcomes, and signals of longer-term impact. The evaluation results are synthesized along project impact pathways while featuring pilot-specific insights and insights on how to further leverage project insights to achieve greater impact in the future.
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Different partners have different roles and responsibilities regarding the outlined activities. Three partners have specific roles regarding SPOON evaluation. AIT coordinates the implementation of the evaluation framework, develops the monitoring toolkit, consolidates and analyzes data submitted by partners, and collects as well as synthesizes insights from formative and final evaluation activities. CSCP establishes and maintains the Impact Board throughout the project duration. HoC contributes to the final evaluation through dedicated expert workshops and provides a synthesis of their results for the final evaluation.

WP leads set up and conduct internal monitoring in line with the evaluation questions and indicators that cover their activities and submit data to AIT, as well as participate in activities related to the formal and final evaluation. The Impact Board, including pilot coordinators and selected local stakeholders, participates in the formative evaluation workshops and facilitates data flows between AIT and the CSLs. Pilot coordinators provide baseline data to AIT, guided by AIT adapt monitoring tools to local contexts and translate evaluation questions to local languages, and report progress to the Impact Board.

The timeline below presents a provisional sequence of activities and their timing, with some flexibility in case of changes in timing across other project activities, in case of overlap with other activities, or to ensure alignment with workshops planned by other partners.

Table 12 Provisional evaluation timeline

Months	Activity	Responsible Partner	Contributing Partners
M11-M12	Consolidating KPIs and monitoring methods for the SPOON Monitoring Toolkit and Formative Evaluation	AIT	WP leads, Pilot coordinators
M13	Online workshop on the monitoring toolkit draft	AIT	All partners
M15	Publication of the monitoring toolkit (version 1)	AIT	All partners
M14-M15	Setting up data collection in line with the SPOON Monitoring Toolkit. Relevant data from earlier project activities is systematized.	AIT	WP leads and Pilot coordinators

M16		WP Leads and Impact Board training: interpreting evaluation data and steering towards impact	AIT	Impact Board, WP Leads
M16		Submitting information on baseline conditions based on a template to be provided by AIT.	Pilot coordinators	
M18		First Annual Formative Evaluation – early implementation progress	AIT	WP and Pilot coordinators, all partners
TBD		Capturing and co-interpreting CSL workshop outputs	Pilot coordinators	SFC, CSCP, knowledge brokers
TBD		Implementing regular feedback loops and course correction using monitoring tools and peer learning	Impact Board	SFC, JIBE, Pilot coordinators, AIT
M22		Monitoring Toolkit iterative update	AIT	All partners
M25		Capacity-building to align BCIs with the impact pathways and local priorities, and explore options to enhance the impact potential of BCIs.	AIT	Impact Board, Pilot coordinators
M25-M30		Engaging citizens and stakeholders to interpret findings and identify gaps	Pilot coordinators	AIT, SFC, Impact Board
M27		Mini-formative Review #2 with focus quality of BCI designs, robustness of monitoring, and data availability	AIT	WP Leads, Pilot coordinators
M30		Annual Formative Evaluation (early BCI insights WP progress, cross-project learning) and identifying options to enhance impact potential	AIT	All partners, Impact Board
M34		Monitoring Toolkit iterative update with feedback from partners	AIT	All partners
M36		Final evaluation first preparation – data consolidation & design of expert workshops	AIT, HoC	All WPs

M41		CSLs and WPS submit the third data package on short-term indicators, interim outcomes, and an update on anticipated long-term impacts.	CSL and WP Coordinators, Impact Board	AIT supports the process
M44		Monitoring Toolkit is published(v2)	AIT	WP2, Pilot coordinators
M44-46		Five expert workshops on SPOON tools across identified dimensions	HoC	WP2, WP4, project stakeholders
M45-M48		Assessing early outcomes and impacts at project end; exploring scalability and replication	AIT	Project partners
M48		Final Impact Evaluation Report (D5.4); Public webinar	AIT	All partners, Impact Board

Further sections will detail the aspects outlined below, excluding the conceptualisation activity as it is covered in this document in a more cross-cutting manner.

4.2 CAPACITY BUILDING

Dedicated capacity-building activities will take place with a focus on understanding and applying the evaluation approach, the use of the monitoring toolkit and specific methods, supporting links between Pilots and SPOON impact pathways, as well as specific activities to support the capacity of each Pilot to deliver on its intended scope of activities. Capacity building will be differentiated across the different target groups: activities targeting WP Leads, Impact Board training, as well as dedicated activities focusing on interactions with specific partners or stakeholders based on identified needs.

4.3 MONITORING AND DATA COLLECTION

SEF will be operationalised via a hands-on SPOON Monitoring Toolkit for CSLs and their activities, with relevant KPIs that align with the evaluation. It will outline the methods, approaches, tools, and scales for measuring and monitoring impact, including input from WPs and CLSs, and dedicated additional activities. It will particularly underline the integration of qualitative and quantitative approaches.

SPOON Monitoring Toolkit (developed under T5.2) serves as a central operational resource, standardising data collection across diverse local settings. It operationalizes the evaluation framework for practical implementation in a hands-on manner. The toolkit functions as a living document that is continuously updated and refined throughout the project lifecycle. This ensures it remains responsive to emerging insights, challenges, and opportunities. Feedback

loops from CSLs will be built into the process to enable timely adaptations, promote shared ownership, and maintain alignment with SPOON's overarching goals.

The SPOON Monitoring Toolkit will provide clear guidance materials, explainers on intended use, data sources, and timing relevance across CSL intervention stages. Ultimately, it acts not only as a monitoring instrument but also as a facilitative learning tool that strengthens adaptive governance and decision-making capacities within and across CSLs.

In SPOON, the data comes mainly from the following broad sources:

- The activities of Work Packages with data collected by WP leads (such as regarding the SPOON Academy, multi-stakeholder recommendations, etc.).
- The CSLs and BCIs: data collected from participants in different regions.
- The SPOON Digital Toolset: data generated through the questionnaire, DataU, Wallet, SPOON Dashboard, and DataLake.
- WP1 survey: data collected to explore barriers and drivers for sustainable and healthy food consumption, based on research gaps and CSL input.

The evaluation will benefit from a range of data types, in line with the SPOON Data Management Plan. The exact data sources will be further detailed within the Monitoring Toolkit and Formative evaluation activities relevant to the scope of each task and specific evaluation needs, as well as considering data availability and limitations.

Table 13 SPOON Evaluation main data sources

Data types	Description
Consumer behaviour data	Information on how people plan, buy, store, prepare, eat, and dispose of food.
Demographic data	Basic participant characteristics such as age, gender, education, household type, and socio-economic profile.
Consent and engagement data	Records of participant agreements on data sharing, frequency of contributions, and interaction with the toolset.
Personal/sensitive data	Limited information that may qualify as personal data under GDPR (e.g., behavioural or demographic data that can make individuals identifiable). No highly sensitive categories (e.g., health, religion) are planned to be collected.
Structured workshop outputs	Data collected systematically through CSL workshops, questionnaires, or defined protocols (e.g., responses to food journey stages).
Unstructured participant contributions	Spontaneous observations, reflections, and qualitative insights shared during CSL activities or through the Digital Toolset.

Digital interaction data	Usage logs and feedback from the SPOON Digital Toolset (questionnaire tool, Food Journal, DataU, Wallet, Dashboard, DATALKE).
Qualitative feedback	Participant reflections and outputs from SPOON Academy trainings, peer learning, and knowledge transfer activities.

Additionally, the Monitoring Toolkit will include a set of diverse monitoring methods, supported by clear guidance materials and explainers on their intended use, timing, and relevance to specific stages of the CSL intervention lifecycle. These methods are designed to be engaging and user-friendly, supporting both high-frequency monitoring and deeper reflection. One tool out of the monitoring toolkit should be applied before, during, or after each major CSL activity.

Table 14 Provisional list of monitoring methods

Method / Instrument	Description
Field-based observations	Retrospective assessment of behavioural patterns and tangible outcomes, with a focus on food waste, sustainable choices, and collective action.
Tailored self-report questionnaires	Adapted to CSL-specific contexts, considering participant demographics and expertise levels.
Light-touch instruments	Includes mini-quizzes, gamified exercises, pulse checks, and Mentimeter polls for real-time feedback during sessions.
Experience Sampling Methods (ESM)	Capture participants lived experiences and project interactions over time.

4.4 FORMATIVE EVALUATION

Formative evaluation is applied as a participatory and reflexive exercise that is conducted annually to track project progress and foster learning, with shorter interim formats as necessary. Formative evaluation ensures that project partners and CSLs remain aligned with the project's expected objectives (those present in the Grant Agreement) while also responding to new knowledge or changing conditions, helping to harness opportunities for impact enhancement. Rather than acting as external auditors, evaluators take on the role of learning partners, working closely with project partners. This participatory approach strengthens ownership, builds capacity, and helps CSLs navigate uncertainties while fostering collective learning (Boni et al., 2023)

KPIs for the formative evaluation are built on the impact pathways outlined in the evaluation framework (5.1) and are further detailed in a co-creative online workshop with CSLs and project partners. After each CSL iteration, data is collected by the Impact Board and reported back to

AIT, followed by an evaluation meeting with each Pilot coordinator. Feedback channels link pilots with work package and task leads, the Impact Board, and evaluation coordinators. This part of the process is tentative and will be agreed between AIT and the respective project partners in the next stages.

Feedback and self-assessments are systematically gathered across key dimensions, covering activities and outcomes, and individual participant experiences. Processes to bring inputs from peer learning and monitoring are provided. By embedding feedback mechanisms, formative evaluation allows for continuous learning, compliance, and, as an adaptive approach, it allows for to enhancement overall impact potential of the project.

Table 15 Key feedback components

Dimension	Description
Evaluation Criteria & Indicators	Feedback and self-assessment use key indicators refined with partners, focusing on ethical standards and transparency in data handling.
Measurement Methods & Data Sources	Multiple sources—citizen scientists, Pilot coordinators, and intermediaries—are integrated into the data management plan.
Data Collection Frequency & Timeframe	Data is collected continuously and at key milestones, balancing early formative insights with long-term impact assessment.
Roles & Responsibilities	Data collection duties are allocated across CSLs and partners; each CSL has a local monitoring coordinator.
Storage & Accessibility	Data is centrally stored in the DATALAKE, following FAIR principles to ensure accessibility and compliance with ethical guidelines.
Contribution to Project Goals	Findings from feedback and self-assessment directly inform understanding of impact on food system transformation and alignment with impact pathways.

4.5 FINAL EVALUATION

The final evaluation will focus on the SPOON processes as well as the achieved results, interim outcomes, and long-term impact potential through triangulation of different sources. It will be based on the data collected throughout the project, such as the data submitted for formative evaluation and insights from formative evaluation workshops, data collected through the digital questionnaire, available statistical data on the SPOON digital toolkit usage, the final updates of data submitted by the WP leads and by the Pilot coordinators through the Impact Board, as well as a series of online expert workshops to be conducted by HoC.

While AIT will analyse submitted data and synthesize insights, the evaluation will strongly rely on a collaborative approach, allowing partners to contribute with their interpretation of

findings, results, interim outcomes, as well as impact potential beyond the project duration along the impact pathways and with insights integrated across different evaluation components. D5.4 Final impact evaluation report will provide a broad narrative highlighting contributions along the SPOON pathways and for each of the pilots, aiming to reflect the achievements within different pilot regions.

The evaluation will also seek to identify options to further enhance the impact potential from a transformative perspective, leveraging insights within and across different pilot regions and contrasting them against broader state-of-the-art knowledge on food system transformation. In case some of the expected outcomes are not fully reached or there are differences between what has been initially anticipated and what has been achieved, there would be space to provide explanations based on project-internal and external factors, as well as devise implications for future food system transformation interventions.

5 CONCLUSION

The framework outlined in this document connects SPOON pathways and to a transformative evaluation approach. It aimed to elaborate on linkages between project objectives, activities, results, outcomes, and impacts, and how their potential can be leveraged and enhanced through evaluation. The framework also presents the main orientations for implementing further activities related to implementation activities. Successful implementation of this framework will depend on uptake and commitment by project partners, and the framework will remain responsive to partner needs and project developments.

REFERENCES

- Boni, A., Velasco, D., Molas-Gallart, J., & Schot, J. (2023). Evaluating transformative innovation policy in a formative way: Insights from Vinnova's food mission experiment. *Research Evaluation*, 32(3), 577–590. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvad029>
- Brons, A., Van Der Gaast, K., Awuh, H., Jansma, J. E., Segreto, C., & Wertheim-Heck, S. (2022). A tale of two labs: Rethinking urban living labs for advancing citizen engagement in food system transformations. *Cities*, 123, 103552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2021.103552>
- Buckton, S. J., Fazey, I., Ball, P., Ofir, Z., Colvin, J., Darby, M., Hejnowicz, A. P., Leicester, G., Newman, R., Page, G. G., Parsons, K., & Van Mierlo, B. (2025). Twelve principles for transformation-focused evaluation. *PLOS Sustainability and Transformation*, 4(4), e0000164. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pstr.0000164>
- Carriedo, A., Walls, H., & Brown, K. A. (2022). Acknowledge the Elephant in the Room: The Role of Power Dynamics in Transforming Food Systems. Comment on “What Opportunities Exist for Making the Food Supply Nutrition Friendly? A Policy Space Analysis in Mexico.” *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.34172/ijhpm.2022.7382>
- Conti, C., Hall, A., Moallemi, E. A., Laila, A., Bene, C., Fanzo, J., Gibson, M. F., Gordon, L., Hicks, C., Kok, K., Rao, N., Laxminarayan, R., & Mason-D’Croz, D. (2025). Top-down vs bottom-up processes: A systematic review clarifying roles and patterns of interactions in food system transformation. *Global Food Security*, 44, 100833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2025.100833>
- Crippa, M., Solazzo, E., Guizzardi, D., Monforti-Ferrario, F., Tubiello, F. N., & Leip, A. (2021). Food systems are responsible for a third of global anthropogenic GHG emissions. *Nature Food*, 2(3), 198–209. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00225-9>
- Davelaar, D. (2021). Transformation for sustainability: A deep leverage points approach. *Sustainability Science*, 16(3), 727–747. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00872-0>
- Dorninger, C., Abson, D. J., Apetrei, C. I., Derwort, P., Ives, C. D., Klaniiecki, K., Lam, D. P. M., Langsenlehner, M., Riechers, M., Spittler, N., & von Wehrden, H. (2020). Leverage points for sustainability transformation: A review on interventions in food and energy systems. *Ecological Economics*, 171, 106570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106570>
- Downs, S. M., Ahmed, S., Fanzo, J., & Herforth, A. (2020). Food Environment Typology: Advancing an Expanded Definition, Framework, and Methodological Approach for Improved Characterization of Wild, Cultivated, and Built Food Environments toward Sustainable Diets. *Foods*, 9(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9040532>
- Edwards, F., Sonnino, R., & López Cifuentes, M. (2024a). Connecting the dots: Integrating food policies towards food system transformation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 156, 103735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103735>
- Edwards, F., Sonnino, R., & López Cifuentes, M. (2024b). Connecting the dots: Integrating food policies towards food system transformation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 156, 103735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103735>

- Eicken, H., Danielsen, F., Sam, J.-M., Fidel, M., Johnson, N., Poulsen, M. K., Lee, O. A., Spellman, K. V., Iversen, L., Pulsifer, P., & Enghoff, M. (2021). Connecting Top-Down and Bottom-Up Approaches in Environmental Observing. *Bioscience*, 71(5), 467–483. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biab018>
- Federica Grant, Vittoria Aureli, & Laura Rossi. (2023). *State of the art of the European food system and behaviour transition*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14223690>
- Fuentes, C., Cegrell, O., & Vesterinen, J. (2021). Digitally enabling sustainable food shopping: App glitches, practice conflicts, and digital failure. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 61, 102546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102546>
- Gibbons, M., Limoges, C., Nowotny, H., Schwartzman, S., Scott, P., & Trow, M. (1994). *The New Production of Knowledge: The Dynamics of Science and Research in Contemporary Societies*. SAGE.
- Granheim, S. I., Løvhaug, A. L., Terragni, L., Torheim, L. E., & Thurston, M. (2022). Mapping the digital food environment: A systematic scoping review. *Obesity Reviews*, 23(1), e13356. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13356>
- Greenthal, E., Marx, K., Friedman, E., John, S., Johnson, J., LiPuma, C., Nara, D., Sorscher, S., Gardner, K., & Musicus, A. (2024). Navigating the online food environment: Policy pathways for promoting food access, transparency, and healthy food choices online. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2024.1473303>
- Hölsgens, R., Wascher, E., Bauer, C., Boll, J., Bund, S., Dankwart-Kammoun, S., Heese, I., Schrot, K., Schultze, J., & Tenambergen, R. (2023). Transdisciplinary Research along the Logic of Empowerment: Perspectives from Four Urban and Regional Transformation Projects. *Sustainability*, 15(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15054599>
- Horcea-Milcu, A.-I., Dorresteijn, I., Leventon, J., Stojanovic, M., Lam, D. P. M., Lang, D. J., Moriggi, A., Raymond, C. M., Stålhammar, S., Weiser, A., & Zimmermann, S. (2024). Transformative research for sustainability: Characteristics, tensions, and moving forward. *Global Sustainability*, 7, e14. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sus.2024.12>
- IFOAM. (n.d.). Food Security Challenges in an EU Context. Retrieved August 28, 2025, from <https://read.organicseurope.bio/publication/eu-food-and-farming-policy-and-food-security/food-security-challenges-in-an-eu-context/>
- Janin, P., Fofiri Nzossié, E.-J., & Rcaud, S. (2023). Governance challenges for sustainable food systems: The return of politics and territories. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 65, 101382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2023.101382>
- Kanger, L., Ghosh, B., & Entsalo, H. (2025). Integrated framework of intervention points and transformative outcomes for single- and multi-system transitions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 216, 124146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2025.124146>
- Kieslinger, B., Schäfer, T., Heigl, F., Dörler, D., Richter, A., & Bonn, A. (2018). Evaluating citizen science: Towards an open framework. In A. Bonn, S. Hecker, M. Haklay, A. Bowser, Z. Makuch, & J. Vogel (Eds.), *Citizen Science* (pp. 81–96). UCL Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv550cf2.13>

- Kieslinger, B., Schuerz, S., Mayer, K., & Schaefer, T. (2022). *CoAct D7.4 Final Impact Assessment Report: Evaluation results, overall impact assessment and final reflections on co-evaluation*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7468546>
- Kok, K. P. W., van der Meij, M. G., Wagner, P., Cesuroglu, T., Broerse, J. E. W., & Regeer, B. J. (2023). Exploring the practice of Labs for sustainable transformation: The challenge of 'creating impact.' *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 388, 135994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.135994>
- Lajoie-O'Malley, A., Bronson, K., van der Burg, S., & Klerkx, L. (2020). The future(s) of digital agriculture and sustainable food systems: An analysis of high-level policy documents. *Ecosystem Services*, 45, 101183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101183>
- Marshall, Q., Fanzo, J., Barrett, C. B., Jones, A. D., Herforth, A., & McLaren, R. (2021). Building a Global Food Systems Typology: A New Tool for Reducing Complexity in Food Systems Analysis. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.746512>
- Moallemi, E., Miller, M., Szetey, K., Chakori, S., Palmer, J., Battaglia, M., Bryan, B. A., Gao, L., Hall, A., Leith, P., Raven, R., & Reed, P. M. (2024). *Entry points for accelerating transitions towards a more sustainable future*. <https://eartharxiv.org/repository/view/6977/>
- Mourre, M.-L., Gonzalez, C., & Djedidi, A. (2024). Can local food become an inclusive practice in urban areas? A community provisioning systems approach. *Recherche et Applications En Marketing (English Edition)*, 39(3), 32–66. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20515707241266350>
- Oakden, L., Bridge, G., Armstrong, B., Reynolds, C., Wang, C., Panzone, L., Rivera, X. S., Kause, A., Ffoulkes, C., Krawczyk, C., Miller, G., & Serjeant, S. (2021). The Importance of Citizen Scientists in the Move Towards Sustainable Diets and a Sustainable Food System. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.596594>
- O'Brien, K., Carmona, R., Gram-Hanssen, I., Hochachka, G., Sygna, L., & Rosenberg, M. (2023). Fractal approaches to scaling transformations to sustainability. *Ambio*, 52(9), 1448–1461. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-023-01873-w>
- OECD. (2021). *Digital opportunities for demand-side policies to improve consumer health and the sustainability of food systems* (OECD Food, Agriculture and Fisheries Papers No. 148; OECD Food, Agriculture and Fisheries Papers, Vol. 148). <https://doi.org/10.1787/bec87135-en>
- Otieno, D., Niewolny, K., Archibald, T., Schenk, T., & Nunoo, N. (2023). Transformative learning to promote transformative evaluation of food system praxis. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 6, 1068356. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2022.1068356>
- Pel, B., & Stirling, A. (2024). *Transforming 'systems': Which? How? Whose? Why? Whither? Whence? System Analysis and Critical Systems Thinking in Transitions Research*. Earth and Environmental Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2024-sc4c3>
- Rambonnet, L., Vink, S. C., Land-Zandstra, A. M., & Bosker, T. (2019). Making citizen science count: Best practices and challenges of citizen science projects on plastics in aquatic environments. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 145, 271–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.05.056>

- Schade, S., Arias, R., Vilariño, F., Vilaseca, H., Reinoso, D., Guasch, B., Roura, S., Recio, L., Bucca, S., Müller, A. P. R., & Riemenschneider, D. (2024). Exploring the marriage of citizen science and living labs; in support of green, social and digital transitions. *ARPHA Proceedings*, 6, 179–184. <https://doi.org/10.3897/ap.e126845>
- Slater, S., Baker, P., & Lawrence, M. (2022). An analysis of the transformative potential of major food system report recommendations. *Global Food Security*, 32, 100610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2022.100610>
- Sonnino, R., Tegoni, C. L. S., & De Cunto, A. (2019). The challenge of systemic food change: Insights from cities. *Cities*, 85, 110–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2018.08.008>
- Southern Denmark University, Kolding, Denmark, & Wilde, D. (2021, August 15). *Rethinking food: Co-creating citizen science for sustainability transitions*. Nordes 2021: Matters of Scale. <https://doi.org/10.21606/nordes.2021.25>
- Tsolakidis, D., Gymnopoulos, L. P., & Dimitropoulos, K. (2024). Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Technologies for Personalized Nutrition: A Review. *Informatics*, 11(3), 62. <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics11030062>
- Turner, C., Aggarwal, A., Walls, H., Herforth, A., Drownowski, A., Coates, J., Kalamatianou, S., & Kadiyala, S. (2018). Concepts and critical perspectives for food environment research: A global framework with implications for action in low- and middle-income countries. *Global Food Security*, 18, 93–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2018.08.003>
- van Noordwijk, T. (C. G. E.), Bishop, I., Staunton-Lamb, S., Oldfield, A., Loisel, S., Geoghegan, H., & Ceccaroni, L. (2021). Creating Positive Environmental Impact Through Citizen Science. In K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, & K. Wagenknecht (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 373–395). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_19
- von Gönner, J., Herrmann, T. M., Bruckermann, T., Eichinger, M., Hecker, S., Klan, F., Lorke, J., Richter, A., Sturm, U., Voigt-Heucke, S., Brink, W., Liedtke, C., Premke-Kraus, M., Altmann, C., Bauhus, W., Bengtsson, L., Büermann, A., Dietrich, P., Dörler, D., ... Bonn, A. (2023). Citizen science's transformative impact on science, citizen empowerment and socio-political processes. *Socio-Ecological Practice Research*, 5(1), 11–33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42532-022-00136-4>
- Wehn, U., Gharesifard, M., Ceccaroni, L., Joyce, H., Ajates, R., Woods, S., Bilbao, A., Parkinson, S., Gold, M., & Wheatland, J. (2021). Impact assessment of citizen science: State of the art and guiding principles for a consolidated approach. *Sustainability Science*, 16(5), 1683–1699. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00959-2>
- ZSI - Centre for Social Innovation, Kieslinger, B., Schürz, S., Mayer, K., & Schaefer, T. (2022). Participatory evaluation practices in citizen social science: Insights from three case studies. *Fteval JOURNAL for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation*, 54, 10–19. <https://doi.org/10.22163/fteval.2022.567>

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